

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN SELFIE TAKING, PHOTO EDITING AND ONLINE POSTING BEHAVIOUR AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

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Selfie taking , photo editing and online posting has become a part of our everyday life. Especially the adolescents are seen to use these aforementioned activities and technologies more often and at higher frequencies.

Aim: The aim is to predict the gender differences that exists in selfie taking , photo editing and online posting behaviour among adolescents.

Materials and methods: A Cross-sectional comparative study was conducted on a group of 100 adolescents. The study participants were divided into two groups of opposite sex . Group A were females and group B were males a questionnaire has been prepared and circulated among the adolescent students of Saveetha Medical college hospital from January 2019 to March 2019. Students aged 18-30 were included in the study.

Results: By analysing the questionnaires answered by the participants it was found that 76% of females take selfie, 62% edit their photos and 69% women share photo in the social media while in the male only 24% take selfie, 31% edit their photos and 38% share photo in the social media.

Conclusion: Females have high selfie taking, photo editing and online posting behaviour among adolescents.

Introduction

Technology is an indispensable part of our day today life, and it is impossible to neglect its impact on human life(1). The technological advances has lead to medical disorder termed “behavioural addiction” which is emerging as psychiatric disorder(2).Taking Selfie has become a huge part in modern life. Selfie is a self portrait type image, usually taken to look casual. The term “selfie” has become popular in the vocabulary of every teen, young, and adult in the technological world and is named Word of the Year in 2013 by the Oxford English Dictionary.

Selfie is defined as “a photograph that one has taken of oneself, one taken with a smartphone or webcam and shared via social media”(3). Posting selfie is one of the most widespread online activities, particularly among adolescents and young adults. According to Lee and Sung people who use smartphones take approximately 93 million selfies every day, and approximately 880 billion photos were shared online in 2014. The act of taking selfies and posting

them on various social media platforms are now very common. Studies, however, link social media use in young adults to various behaviour development issues(4).

Photo editing applications are used to crop and touch up photos. Usually it is done by magazines to make people look more appealing. Social media facilitates interaction between large groups of people. Social media was actually initiated for the online businesses. This research is done to analyse the social media usage among the adolescents and also to predict the disparity amongst females and males. Females were more likely to take selfies, post selfies, crop photos and use photographic filters compared to males. Adolescents were found to be more likely than young adults to take own and group selfies, post selfies, and use photo editors. The predictive effect was stronger among women than among men regarding selfie taking, posting and editing behaviour(5).

Despite the popularity of selfies there are few studies that specifically explore selfie taking and their consequences. Therefore this current research is designed assess the selfie taking , editing and posting pattern and behaviour among the adolescents and also to assess the gender differences in the above mentioned activities.

Materials and methods

A Cross-sectional comparative study was conducted on a group of 100 adolescents. The study participants were divided into two groups of opposite sex. Group A were females and group B were males. The purpose of the research is to predict the gender differences existing in selfie taking ,photo editing and online posting behaviour, to deal with this various articles have been referred and to validate it more accurately , a questionnaire has been prepared and circulated among the adolescent students of Saveetha Medical college hospital from January 2019 to March 2019. Students aged 18-30 were included in the study after obtaining Ethical approval from the Institutional Ethics Board, Saveetha Medical college and Hospital (SMC/IEC/2018/11/336). Prior written informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

Statistical analysis: Then the data was entered in database Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 21. Statistical analysis of the data was done using Data analysis was done using Fisher's exact test and P value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results

By analysing the questionnaire, it was found that female tend to take more selfie and edit their photos more often and share their photos in social media more than their male counterparts.

Table 1:

	Male N (%)	Female N (%)
Take selfie	24	76
Share photo in the social media	31	69
Edit their photos	38	62

Table 1 shows that 76% of females take selfie, 62% edit their photos and 69% women share photo in the social media while in the male only 24% take selfie, 31% edit their photos and 38% share photo in the social media.

In addition to the following details it was also concluded by analysing the questionnaires that 20%of adolescents tend to take a selfie everyday, 32.5% take a selfie once a week and 48.8% take a selfie very rarely. Present study found that 77.6% of students take a selfie when well dressed up , 76.3% students take selfie during any special occasions and 17.1% of participants take a selfie merely everyday.In this study is was found that 71.1%of adolescents post their photos in various social media for fun that is for no specific reason,42.2% of them post it online to let people know their day,28.1% share their photos to share information and 26.6% post their photos to

communicate with specific person. More than two third of the participants (>80%) post at least one to five photos in social media every week ,and 7.3% of participants post five to ten or more than ten photos per week in different social media. Majority of college going adolescents (70%) share specific photos of them visit places as in vacations which is more than people who share photos of them when well dressed up (67%) ,also 29.2% of them share pictures showing their achievements and 4.6% of participants post every photo they take in different social cites . In the present study ,55.6% of participants edit the background themes in their photos , 44.4% edit body features and add beauty filters in their photos and self portraits and 31.5% add animal filters to the photos.

Discussion

This research paper is more concerned with assessing the gender difference that exist among adolescents in the aforementioned activities. The study shows that women tend to take more selfies , edit it and also share it online . The results of this study were consistent with research conducted by Manovich et. al it was found that females take more selfies as compared to males. Another research conducted by Glum et al, supports the findings of this study, he found that females take 1.3 time more selfies than males (6).

It has shown that attention seeking behaviour motivates selfie-posting online (7). A study has explained that three principal motivations behind taking selfie: self-approval, belonging, and documentation. Self-approval was negatively related to: conscientiousness, emotional stability, openness to experiences, and self-esteem, and positively correlated to frequent checking for “likes.” Belonging was related to openness to experiences. Documentation was related to agreeableness and extroversion (8). Women aged 18 to 29 years share selfies in order to accumulate “likes,” and the quality of a selfie depends on lighting, and posture. The study also found that selfies allow women to experiment with new and different looks(9).

The findings of this study are consistent with the results of studies conducted by another study in which they found that majority of the respondents show selfie taking behaviours and they browse social media regularly. Overall, the empirical evidence obtained from the analysis was in line with the hypotheses (11). More specifically, these results were consistent with previous research found that narcissistic individuals who liked to create self-impressions were more prone to engaging in unhealthy behaviors that helped them to fulfill their desire (12).

Conclusion

From the detailed analysis of the answers from the questionnaire it was brought to a conclusion that the usage of technologies like selfies and photo editing by the adolescents is to represent themselves and their lives better in the social media . This also shows that the adolescent participants uses the photo editors to make their appearance even more better ,and the posting behaviour in social media is to share their life happenings more than communicating with people. It was also concluded that women tend to use the above mentioned technologies than men of their age .

Limitations: It is a cross-sectional study so causal relationships cannot be inferred. Thus, a study that employs longitudinal data collection will be required to address this issue better.

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